
Assessing the status of funding for public service delivery in Tanzania: A case study of Ilala city council, Dar es salaam

Islam, Halima¹

Revocatus Kabobe²

islajen9@gmail.com¹

kaboberevocatus@gmail.com²

^{1,2}The Open University of Tanzania (OUT)

ABSTRACT

Funding is very significance for effective public service delivery. The limited understanding on the status of funding hindered public service operation. This study assessed the status of funding for public service delivery in Ilala City Council, Dar es salaam -Tanzania. It was based on administrative service delivery. This case study research design was grounded in interpretivism philosophy and a qualitative approach. It employed semi structured interview, field observation and document review for data collection. The study carried out unknown sample size which was determined using saturation point with the application of purposive and snowball sampling techniques. The data was collected from the local government officials and the community members. This study used thematic and content analysis. However, the study revealed several causes of inadequate funding such as low internal revenue collection, insufficient budget allocation, poor implementation of waste collection budget, poor implementation of inter revenue collection policy, lack of continuous general auditing, donor dependency, lack of community involvement in decision making boards and lack of enough encouragement between public - private partnership. The research determined numerous effects including the long waiting hours, shortage of resources, poor productivity, lack of morale and commitments, lack of awareness on the availability of services and opportunities provided by City Council, lack of enough financial support to small business owners, Stress and conflict on public service delivery. The study expected to eradicate the problem by adopting the community engagement in decision making boards and others.

Key words: Funding, Public service delivery, administrative service, inadequate funds.

1. INTRODUCTION

Funding is a critical input that enabled public service sectors to manage the fundamental activity of delivering public service such as administrative service. Adequate funding was crucial in improving service delivery in public administration because it ensured that resources were available to meet the needs of the population effectively (World Health Organization, 2021). Key ways in which adequate funds may contribute to better service delivery include capacity building and access to quality resources. Inadequate funds recognized in undermining the ability of the government to deliver public service, caused poor economic decision and a high increase in delays (Durdyev & Hosseini, 2020).

Globally, A study by Ramírez de la Cruz et al. (2020) underlined the status of funding that, inadequate funding allocated for the health service sector in Mexico and Brazil resulted into fail in maintaining the quality of services in public administration due to the shortage of financial resources. Shaturaev (2022) elucidated the funding level for being inadequate on the government budget which was then impacting the quality of education system in Indonesia.

In the developing countries such as Nigeria, Ghana, Namibia and South Africa address inadequate funding brought about the weak financial resource allocation, inadequate budgeting and late to release funds for implementation of the budget (Atuilik et al., 2019; Yamoah, 2024; Rulashe & Dyana, 2022; Kalonda & Govender, 2021). Atiku et al. (2023) stipulated that, the government budget was the main sources of funding in Namibia while a study by Odediji et al. (2023) revealed on the lower funding allocation to the education service sector.

Tanzania had been facing a problem on the status of funding like other developing countries in which a study by Wawa (2020) affirmed about insufficient situation of funding which affects the work of maintaining or upgrading the existing facilities at Dodoma City Council. Mankambila and Marwa (2024) highlighted about donor funding in the healthy sector despite the lack of adequate financial management capacity at the local level caused the withdrawal of donor support. Other studies claimed over funding inadequacy affects the administrative authority to be overwhelmed with unfavorable system like limited revenue sources and caused local government remains dependent for 80-90% financially to central government (Respy & Mrindoko, 2024; Lameck & Kinemo, 2021).

In Ilala City Council, the status of funding formerly frustrated the activity of delivering public service. A study by Mbogella et al. (2024) indicated on the existence of financial challenges like limited funds, inadequate funding, delay in funds disbursement and relocation of funds resulting into poor performance and incomplete of project in agriculture, water, health, and TASAF. Gasto (2020) recognized a great effort which made by Ilala City Council such as the introduction of Service agreement but still faces a problem like high increase of delays in paying workers' salaries and inadequate funds for administrative costs. However, this study in Tanzania was very important since the community had less trust over local government decisions for instance in managing cash transfer programs to the lower level of authority (Evans et al., 2019).

Following the above explanation, there had been various considerable efforts such as adoption of administrative reforms, fiscal decentralization and financial management reforms have been done to deal with funding issues which approximately embarked from 1980s to 1990s (Lameck & Kinemo, 2021; Klenk & Reiter, 2019; Lam & Yang, 2020). The Other strides undertaken included establishing Anticorruption bodies like PCCB and cutting off unnecessary expenditure. Ngwega (2023) disclosed several mechanisms in Tanzania for improving management of public funds such as financial laws, regulation and guidelines,

segregation of duties, budget, technological system, audit committee and frequent internal audit. Despite all these efforts, the level of funding was still a problem in many municipalities found in Tanzania including Ilala City Council.

Mainly, this study focused on assessing the status of funding for public service delivery. Corresponding to that, there was a lack of comprehensive assessments that clearly introduced the current status of funding. This study wished to bridge a gap which drawn by partial understanding of the fact due to scarcity of empirical materials evidence. Jacob et al. (2021) affirmed the causes of inadequate funds for education services in Nigeria which were the poor government allocation, low school fees, corruption and poor planning resulting into poor quality education. This study opted to contribute on the status of funding in Tanzania basing on administrative service in Ilala City Council. On the other side, for a proper addressing of this serious problem, the study used two theories inclusively which were the institutional theory and Resource dependency theory.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Understanding the status of funding was significant in public administration for ensuring better public service delivery particularly on administrative service. The existence of funding issues and delay in funds disbursement affirmed to hinder the efficient execution of responsibilities for the agriculture, water, health, and TASAF services in Ilala City Council (Mbogella et al., 2024). Jacob et al. (2021) highlighted about the condition of funding being inadequate for education service affects the administration of universities. Yet, Studies like Lameck and Kinemo (2021) and Rulashe and Dyana (2022) stipulated on the deficit budgets which affect business operations, caused local governments to become dependent financially on the central government, limit revenue collection and affected the quality of education and health services. Despite that, the status of funding remained as a major challenge on service delivery in Ilala City Council. When this problem wouldn't be addressed, it would leave the community with less trust to the local government's decisions (Mbogella et al., 2024). Furthermore, many recent studies such as Odediji et al. (2023), Jacob et al. (2021) and Shaturaev (2022) concentrated much in addressing different topics such as analyzing the funding situation, causes and effects of inadequate funds in Education service. Despite that, still the existing studies left a gap in understanding the current status of funding for public service delivery specifically on administrative service in Ilala City Council. A significant of addressing this gap was relied on the need of having sufficient current studies which contribute on improving public service delivery, eliminate poverty, excessive employment, economic development and fostering trust. However, this study focused on assessing the status of funding for public service delivery in Tanzania particularly in Ilala City Council, Dar es Salaam.

1.2 Research Questions

- i. What are the causes of inadequate funds for public service delivery?
- ii. What are the effects of inadequate funding for public service delivery?
- iii. What are the measures taken against inadequate funds to enhance public service delivery?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

2.1.1 Institutional Theory

The institutional theory was introduced by Douglass North in 1970s. This theory focuses much on elaborating how the existence of challenges in various institutions

contributed by the poor institutional system, historical legacy, the organization structures, institutional norms, rules, rigid budgeting procedures and many others like bureaucratic procedures. This economist idea was applied in the study for proper dealing with funding issues. In public administration, not only economic factors influencing the institutional capacity but also the institutional or internal factors often create a framework within the organization in which operate, influences their decision making, resource allocation and service delivery (Mbogella et al., 2024). The theory emphasized that, the public organization shaped by rules, norms, values, tradition and social expectations. Following this, when the institution fails to maintain normal results into the funding shortfalls.

In the case of Ilala City Council, the institutional norms and bureaucratic structures shaped the way funds are allocated and managed. The budgeting procedures, legal frameworks, and administrative regulations serve as formal institutional rules that governed the resources for public services. For instance, when the Council continued to follow past practices like inadequate budget distribution or outdated financial model led to a problem.

This theory also highlighted the essential of adhering with the organizational structures, practices and policies for sustainable public administration. It helped to explain why certain insufficient funding practices persist, even when reforms adopted. This theory was a core in understanding internal governance constraints and organizational culture which hindered the effective allocation of funds for administrative service. However, this theory was weak since it based much on the internal factors and forgot about the external factors which were also very crucial in understanding funding issues. The identified weakness covered by applying resource dependency theory.

2.1.2 Resource Dependency Theory

The resource dependency theory developed by Jeffrey Pfeffer and Gerald R. Salancik in 1978. For the organization to be successful in attaining the administered goals should depend on the external sources of funding such as Grants and taxes. This theory laid an important lens on how the Ilala City Council interdependent on the external environment to ensure the effectiveness of the service delivery. The theory emphasized the adaptation of resources when it was insufficient so that to maintain its functionality and for the survival of the organization (Zehir, 2019). The public institutions depend on external resources like central government and Donors in which made them vulnerable when resources are restricted and even power imbalances affected funding access.

This theory helped to explain how limited funding from the central government or donors affected the service delivery. Therefore, the Council may adjust its strategies to seek for alternative funding sources for improvement of service delivery in Ilala City Council. These theoretical approaches enabled the analysis of the causes of inadequate funds, the effects on administrative service and measures taken including the reforms and external relationship management in Ilala City Council.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study aimed to assess the status of funding for public service delivery in Tanzania specifically at Ilala City Council, focusing on analyzing the causes, effects and the solution. This theoretical framework illustrates on how institutional and dependence theory provided the foundation of the entire study basically on considering the research specific objectives. This theoretical framework demonstrated how the status of funding can be influenced. The status of funding can be assessed with tools like interview, observation and document review. In understanding the causes, effects and the measures taken, the

institutional budget reviewed and the dependency level, interviewing the local government officials to analyze the misalignment between the institutional mandate and the resources in understanding the prevailing issues. It included the performance audits, observation of the service delays or staff morale, citizen satisfaction and adopting the solution like the institutional capacity building in Ilala City council

Figure 2.1: Theoretical framework

Sources: Developed by the researcher based on the theoretical literature (2025)

2.3 Empirical Literature Review

2.3.1 Causes of Inadequate Funds for Public Service Delivery

In the global, Shaturaev (2022) looked on the financial public education in Indonesia. He managed to assess the countries education performance and provided that, inadequate funds caused by politics and power.

In Africa, Jacob et al. (2021) conducted a case study on evaluating the causes of inadequate funds in Nigeria Public universities. The study applied survey design which carried out within three universities selected federal universities from North central Geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The population was the academic staff from all three selected area. A study Used simple random technique to collect data from 100 lecturers in each three selected area to make a total of 300. A study revealed the causes of inadequate funds in Nigeria Public universities which were poor Planning/Project, poor research income, poor government allocations, poor contribution from the private, institutional corruption, Low internal generated revenue and Low school fees.

Mfugale and Mollel (2024) conducted a study in Tanzania concerning the Accountability of Health Facility Governing Committees and its implications to Health Services Delivery. A study obtained across sectional study design with Simple random sampling, purposive and convenience sampling techniques. Interviewed 98 from council Health Management team, Health Facilities Governing Committees and health staff. A study stipulated that, inadequate funds which faces committees in accomplishing their roles and responsibilities caused by inadequate government budgets and supplements. These findings were relevant in improving service delivery in Ilala City Council.

2.3.2 Effects of Inadequate Funding for Public Service Delivery

Globally, Revko et al. (2020) carried out a study in Ukraine and Poland regarding a Methodology for assessing the influence of cultural infrastructure on regional development. The study applied Perkal's synthetic ratio method in analysis spatial units such as scale for identifying the characteristics of culture infrastructure. The researchers argued that, inadequate funding is being the underlying barriers to access cultural infrastructure.

In Africa context, Jacob et al. (2021) on the study of investigating the causes of inadequate funds in Nigeria Public universities identified numerous effects of inadequate funding such as, poor teaching and learning, poor planning development programme, shortage of staff, poor research programme, strike action in public universities, Poor quality of Education and inadequate facilities.

Mbogella et al. (2024) handled a study on Analysis of Human and Financial Resources as Drivers of Project Success in Local Governments in Tanzania. The study used content analysis to analyze the qualitative data. Interviewed 1002 staffs on the projects related to agriculture, water, health and TASAF. Through which the study highlighted that inadequate funding led to poor performance, shortage of qualified manpower and limited funds. The addressed findings were relevance to be considered because reflect with the recent challenge faces Ilala City Councils.

2.3.3 Measures Taken Against Inadequate Funds to Enhance Public Service Delivery

Revko et al. (2020) on a study of Methodology for assessing the influence of cultural infrastructure on regional development in Ukraine in which suggested that the government should improve financing system of cultural infrastructure through the use of effective state and local budgets, international funds and social participation of local communities.

In Africa, Jacob et al. (2021) based on a Nigeria study of investigating the causes of inadequate funds in Nigeria Public universities suggested the following; The government should release adequate funds or increase the funding of the public university in Nigeria, The School administrators in Nigerian public universities should look inward and come up with strategies to increase the internally generated revenue for the universities, the government and school administrators should encourage the private sector to contribute to the funding of Public universities in Nigeria, the government through the National Universities Commission required to source for funds from international organization for the funding of public universities, Government should ensure that it releases all funds allocated for the administration of public universities on time for the development of the universities and involvement of anticorruption agencies.

Mbogella et al. (2024) indicated that, the study suggested the government to devise robust measures to ensure that both financial resources and human capital were converted to be the best input for project success. The findings of these studies showed the incredible efforts which did to eliminate the problem which relates with the specific objectives in the study of funding in Ilala City Council.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Approach

This study adopted qualitative approach to understand the feelings and attitudes of the participants towards funding issues. The rational of choosing Qualitative research approach was to collect non numerical data and gaining new insights by gathering individual's point of view through interview, observation and document review in a sufficient explanation (Muzari

et al, 2022). These assumptions reflected with the focus of the study's specific objectives on analyzing the causes of inadequate funds, examining the effects of inadequate funding and the suggestions.

3.2 Research Design

For convenient dealing with variety of funding issues the study employed a case study research design. This design involved the collection of data and analysis of qualitative data to explore the funding issues. It was guided with multiple methods of data collection for better attending the specific objectives. The qualitative methods in a case study were very essential in determining the causes and effects which was directly reflecting with the needs of the study's specific objectives (Kamal, 2019).

3.3 Area of the Study

This study carried out at Ilala City Council Dar es salaam Tanzania. The Ilala Municipality has 365km square and comprises of 23 wards (Karondo & Tumaini, 2021). It was the urban City which was highly populated area with pretty opportunity preferable for business activity. The area had a challenge on funding issues specifically in administrative service. This area of study selected purposively by considering the vastness of the Municipal Council and the desire of conducting unique study which was not yet covered (Nduguru, 2023).

3.4 Population of the Study

The targeted populations for the study were the local government officials such as financial officers, administrators/administrative officers, frontline service providers, planners and the community members such as residents of Ilala Municipality, small business owners.

3.5 Sample Size

This study hadn't predefined sample size but employed saturation point approach to determine the appropriate sample size for the qualitative data collection. The number of participants guided by the principle of data saturation such that at the point where no substantial emergence of new themes or insights led to an end of data collection. To carry on, the initial codebook and thematic table prepared for member checking and analysis emerged data simultaneously. For the interview method used the approach of observing if no new code or themes emerge in 3 to 4 consecutively to reach the saturation point. For the observation and document analysis applied the same criteria in tracking the saturation themes.

3.6 Sampling Techniques

Purposive and snowball sampling technique used effectively in obtaining the key informants. In implementing purposive technique to all participants, the study considered the role, position, the experience held for at least 2 to 3 years and knowledge or familiar with funding issues in Ilala City Council. It was also considered the willingness and the ability to participate in interviewing or providing relevant documents.

For the snowball technique, the study adopted linear snowball sampling in which the sample collected by starting with one individual and then, that individual referred the other. The referrals invited with the strategy of requesting the participants to refer 1 to 2 members having experience or knowledge on funding within Ilala City Council.

3.7 Data Collection Methods

This study used semi-structured interviews to collect data. The study offered open ended questions which covered on funding issues including the causes of the challenge,

effects and suggestions for improvements. It was also involved the field observation where by the researcher attended physically to the study area and systematic reviewing of the available documents for further information. The researcher closely checked the reliable current information which suited the study, systematically basing on the research objectives and recognized the sources. These methods provided accurate answers.

3.8 Data Analysis

This study involved thematic analysis and content analysis to analyze the qualitative data from the semi structured interviews, observation and document review systematically.

3.9 Validity and Reliability

This study was obtained content validity by applying pilot testing and consulting other experts before collecting data in the field whereby the study expected to use more than one instrument to ensure the validity of findings. On the other hand, for ensuring consistence of data the study conducted reliability by ensuring durability of instruments and the accuracy of data.

3.10 Ethical Considerations

The ethical consideration in this study was ensured that, the researcher received a letter from Open University of Tanzania and a permit from Ilala city council before starting data collection. Moreover, in considering the ethical issue thus the informed consent was obtained from all participants prior for data collection. In strengthening that, the confidentiality and anonymity of participants were ensured throughout the research process thus the data stored securely and used only for the purpose of this research study. Arifin (2018) supported that, ethical consideration assists to remove interviewee's stress in expressing their feelings during the interview session. However, the aim of considering this part was to maintain integrity, protecting the participants and to ensure validity of the findings.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Causes of Inadequate Funds for Public Service Delivery

Low internal revenue collection

One of the main causes of inadequate funds for public service delivery was the low internal revenue collection. It was found during interview and in the document reviewing. The institution was unable to collect sufficient funds to align with the demand of the service provision. There was high demand of funds in the administration to fit the requirement for the administrative service provision. On the other hand, the study reveals that the low internal revenue collection weakened the financial base though which makes difficult to sustain administrative service delivery. This finding corroborates with those of National Audit Office of Tanzania (2022-24), which confirmed that, many municipal Councils such as the Ilala City Council in Dar es salaam failed to meet the internal revenue collection target. In expanding this one interviewee said,

“Mostly, our service depends much on our own sources of funds, when we fail to collect enough funds due to weak enforcement then it impacts allot on the service provision” (P24, 16 July, 2025 ,11:45am).

Insufficient budget allocation on public service delivery

The findings revealed about insufficient budget allocation on public service delivery. It was happened when the institution expecting to get adequate budget for the service and then it became vice versa to the extent of hindering the recommended service sector provider. The funds which allocated for administrative service delivery was insufficient to meet the needs. The Ilala strategic plan (2021) highlighted about less funds were received by the Council. This continued to reveal that, the service delivery in Ilala City Council depends much on the local sources of funding such as fees. Meanwhile, the internal sources of funds revealed inadequately collected. The implication of this causes some administered projects fail to facilitate its functions properly. Furthermore, it reduces the employee's motivation and comfortability at the work place. One male interviewed respondent said,

“One of the critical challenges which we normally face is the overestimation of revenue target through which lead to budget deficit. This contributes much delay on implementation of development project” (P24, 16 July, 2025 ,11:45am).

Poor implementation of waste collection budget

Another reason of inadequate funds was the poor implementation of waste collection budget. This contributed to the inability of services provision to the Ilala City Council. It was captured during interview and even in document reviewing. The provision of funds described to have an element of delays. Meanwhile, the funds which required for the service was arrived late in which hindered the program of waste collection. Corresponding to this, the findings led to waste mismanagement due to poor implementation of the planed budget. Other implication of the findings led to overspending of the internal funds. In line to this, the findings were consistence with those of (NAOT, 2024) in which shows that the funds comprise with certain features of delays. It was also shared with one female respondent that,

“The problem always, arise when the planed project frequently late to receive funds which leads to unexpected stop of the recommended operation. However, it creates negative perception to the masses around the project. Sometimes it can lead to a certain negative trending news which can take time to clear.” (P16, 14 July, 2025, 10:30am).

Poor implementation of internal revenue collection policy

The study discovered the existence of poor implementation of internal revenue collection policy. This led to the high increase of public complaints and dissatisfaction on the service delivery. This was contributed with the low enforcement of the adopted policies. It was found during interview as well to the document reviewing. The little enforcement on the internal revenue collection policy contributed much to the extent of low internal revenue collection and delays. However, the study unlocked the availability of few expertise through which contributed to reduce the income of the institutions. In a perfect explanation, the policies which kept for improving local revenue collection were not properly enforced. These views supported by NATO (2022 -2024) and in Ilala strategic plan (2021-25).One male respondent said,

“Possibly, there are few expertise to implement policies regarding administration to our City Council because when they introduce any policy, they should make follow up so that to know if the policy works

properly. For instance, it seems that, the revenue collection is the main source of funding in Ilala City Council. Therefore, they might fail in one way or another to collect enough funds due to poor implementation of the policy. That's why, there are allot of delays on service delivery (P9, 8 July, 2025, 16:00pm).

Lack of community involvement in decision making boards

This was another challenge which contributed to inadequate funds in Ilala City Council. The study revealed during interview that, the community members lacked an access of participating in essential matters. The exclusion of community in decision making led to one-sided decisions. This contributed to the occurrence of economic disparity in the institution due to the inconsistency decision making in budgeting and financial planning. It was also led to the existence of several complaints to the community on missing some of administration opportunities. Moreover, one female interviewee added same views,

“Personally, I don't know if our opinions are better considered because I don't see any proper action taken. We as their stakeholder always remain complaining on the side of administrative service. Honestly, I always get involved in other services such as education service. I had been contributing in term of opinions and even for money whoever needed for the betterment of the service for the potential of my kids. However, they need to adopt that approach” (P13, 9 July, 2025, 12:00am).

Lack of continuous general auditing

The findings revealed during interview that, there was lack of continuous general auditing to the Ilala City Council which contributed to the poor service delivery. The occurrence of this challenge reduces donors and community trust. Apart from that, it was revealed to weaken the budgeting discipline and discouraged the external funding sources. The other view of the study, is the failure to conduct continuous general auditing reduces institution's income and unable them to attain the administration's expectations. In further, one female interviewee said,

“In insuring proper provision of service, we need to emphasis as well on the continuous general auditing. When this position becomes inadequately conducted over us hinder the targeted goals” (P16, 14 July, 2025, 10:30am).

Donor dependency

The study revealed about donor dependency being a reason of inadequate funds for public service delivery. The inability of the donors to provide sufficient funds on time discovered in the interview and the available documents. In other circumstances, the institution was unable to cope with the donor's requirement of funding. The unfavorable conditions which kept by the donors led to mismanagement of project and unexpected delays increased on service. The findings were consistency with those of the Ilala City Council Strategic plan (2021-25) in which supported that, the failure of service delivery was due to the delays and disbursement of funds from the donors or central government. However, one respondent said.

“One of a challenge which faces the Ilala City Council, is the delays in funds provision in some projects which practiced by providers” (P11, 9 July ,2025, 8:50am).

Lack of enough encouragement among the Public – private partnership

The study recognized the lack of enough encouragement among public – private partnership. The low efforts which put in place on fostering collaboration between the public and private sectors discovered during interview to cause insufficient of funds. The findings noted the lack of clear or limited policy and framework, challenges the private investors in collaborating with the government entities. This has implication that, the private investors miss some of opportunities which provided by the public sector as well as the institution reduces the availability of funds. One respondent said,

“The private sectors are not all clearly aware to the opportunities which provided by the municipality” (P11, 9 July ,2025, 8:50am).

4.2 Effects of Inadequate Funding for Public Service Delivery

Long waiting hours.

The long waiting hours was an issue in the provision of public service in Ilala City Council. This was obtained in interview and observation process. The study explained that, time management is an important asset in any activity, when it considered in accordance the improvement of service become achievable. Surprisingly, the study respondents unlocked that the administrative service faces a challenge of mismanagement of time through which impacting the community in collecting the administrative service. Corresponding to this, the community members suffer to the extent of being uncomfortable with the service provided. The study affirmed that, the long waiting hours frustrated the community members and erosion of trust in administrative service. In addition to that, one male respondent shared related views

“The time for the provision of service depend on the people attended at the day. This is a problem to us whom are small business holder. In fact, standing in queues for long and postpone on service became normal condition. This costing us a lot on the side of our economic activities, lead us to fail in managing our personal programs” said (P12, 9 July, 2025, 9:05am).

Shortage of resources in the municipality

The shortage of resources became a vast challenge since revealed in all three methods of data collection which were the interview, observation and document review. The interviewees shared that inadequate funding contributes to the scarcity of resources in public administration. The findings observed numerous people were waiting for the service through which signify the presence of inadequate resources. The study also signifies that, the shortage of resources undermines the inputs needed for efficient administration. Moreover, the Ilala City Council strategic plan (2021-25) highlighted the incurred challenge. With regard of the vastness of the challenge, one female interviewee didn't hesitate to say about the problem.

“This is a big institution in which do a variety of things. On respect to the better service provision, it required to have enough materials to enable smooth running of the activities (P23, 16 July, 2025, 11:30am).

Poor productivity

The study was discovered the availability of poor productivity. This was associated much with the presence of delays on service delivery. The study revealed that, the presence of too much delays and inefficiencies in administrative service delivery affects the community members' daily activities. It was captured during interview method and reminded that, much time consuming in getting service was among of the reason of poor production or low output for a day to the small business owners. However, inadequate funding reduces the efficient on performance basically on economic activities. On regards of its barrier, one male respondent said,

“For instance, at the moment I struggle to receive service is how it becomes worse to my business operation” (P14, 9 July, 2025, 13.20pm).

Lack of morale and commitment

Mostly, the study revealed the problem of inadequate funding reduced staff morale and commitment at work. The study respondents had also reported the problem impacting the working performance. The conducive environment of works should include the satisfaction of the service provided. Unexpectedly, the respondents explained that, when the service receivers frequently complain the provider may experience a range of emotional about the problem through which reduces commitment and morale due to the provider feeling unappreciated. One female respondent said,

“ when the citizen becoming much complaining, it means they are not satisfying with our service so when it happens frequently reduces the morale of work” (P22,16 July, 2025, 11:00am).

Lack of awareness on the availability of services and opportunities provided by the administration of Ilala City Council.

It was found that the community members were not aware of some important issues as some of them questioned about which administrative services and opportunities provided by the administration of Ilala City Council. It added that, the existence of inadequate funding revealed to affect the ability of local institution on raising awareness among them. The Ilala City Council strategic plan (2021-25) indicated a barrier of inadequate community awareness which included the poor understanding of administrative procedures, tax function and even where the funds go. This also approved to affect the internal revenue collection. In additional to that, the results found the community members had little understanding on the available services. Evidently, one male community member said:

“To my side, I don't know what kind of administrative services provided by Ilala City Council. I was in a thought that, I'm not alone with this challenge. Unfortunately, I wasn't being able to raise my concern to anywhere. To my opinion there could be an organized institutions or program which assist to raise awareness so that we become familiar with what they normally do. It could be very potential to all of us” (P11, 9 July, 2025, 8:50am).

Lack of enough financial support to small business owners

The results revealed about less financial support to the small business owners though which make them hard in extending to another level. The interviewed study participants

shared about the lack of suitable techniques or policy to serve them in which undermined their capacity to grow. The small business owners always get stuck at the initial stage of development and others drop. It was indicated that, the incapacity of staff contributing much to the lack of enough financial support due to the situation of funding being inadequacy to the local government institution. The same views provided by one female respondent.

“I, as among of the small business owner, I can say that we don’t get enough support in term of financial. Previously, we advised to apply loan but the condition kept for it was inappropriate to some of us. For instance, providing loan in a group is risk to my view because if one will not be able to pay back, all members become responsible. (P4, 2 July, 2025 16:10pm).

Stress and conflict on service delivery

The study noted the existence of stress and conflict on service delivery in which revealed to occur in both, thus to the employees and to the community members. Both the interview and observation methods approved the challenge in a consistency way. The service receivers remained in a dilemma sometimes when the situation changed without adequate explanation. It happened that, the community standing in a queue or kept pending for long for the service. Some respondents had sorts of unanswered questions in their mind like what are they going to do if they late to their daily planned activities. In line with this, one respondent was observed so stressed when travelled for longer to Ilala city with expectation of his issue to be solved on time but wasn’t a like. In connection to this, the same view was given by one male interviewee.

“I was thinking, what will happen if today I will late to operate my business because I have no permanent area. He continued that, for us small business owners when we miss even one day it causes a big trouble because some of us business is everything for our family needs” (P7, 8 July, 2025, 14:20pm).

On the other hand, the study tried to interprets about the conflict between the service receivers and the service providers due to the issue of delays on service delivery. Apart from that, the study showed the presence of institution conflict though which caused by the scarce resources whereby there were insufficient office equipment’s through which led to other staffs blame the management for poor budget management. On the other hand, most of respondents observed complaining about the issue of long waiting hours and delays during service delivery. However, the findings proved that, inadequate funding results into stress and conflict on public service delivery. Additionally, one male respondent provided same views,

“If we persist with this improper system, we will continue to face quarrels and personal conflict because none of us agree to waste time” (P9, 8 July, 2025, 16:00pm).

Another, respondent said.

“People do complain even if you provide elaboration to them.....” (P23, 16 July, 2025, 11:30am)

4.3 Measures Taken Against Inadequate Funds to Enhance Public Service Delivery Community engagement in decision making boards

The essential of community engagement in decision making boards was discovered frequently in interview and document reviewing. The study emphasized that, the community engagement system mostly doing great in improving service delivery. It enables gathering of new perspectives from the community members in which conveniently understand the problem which surrounding them. Participation of community members in crucial matters such as planning and budgeting specifically on decision making allow them to provide valuable inputs which improve service delivery in public administration. The exclusion of community members in decision making boards create decisions that do not reflect the local needs. The study emphasized that, the community members remained poorly informed and didn't participate fully in decisions. In line with this, the Ilala City Council strategic plan (2021-25) supported the findings by putting them on the lists of important agenda for the Municipal plan. However, one female respondent said,

“I think Ilala City Council should look for new proper system which will become useful to us in offering a room of providing opinions on essential matters” (P13, 9 July, 2025, 12:00am).

Another measure taken was the internal capacity building in public service delivery

The results proposed the consideration of internally capacity building in public service delivery basically in administrative service delivery. This was discovered in interview and document review that, the internal capacity building in public service delivery plays a critical role in improving administrative service delivery and the institution performance. It was prolonged that, the employees become more equipped to their specialization. Other respondents were opined that, there should be clear procedures, accountability frameworks and proper decision-making process. This included the provision of continuous training, seminar and strengthening of the internal system to ensure the institution operate under effective rules. The Ilala City Council strategic plan (2021-25) emphasized about the internal capacity building in public service delivery through which issues like staff training had been justified. Despite that, one male interviewee said.

“We advise the government to continue in offering adequate training to their staff members so that to make them competent in their obligation” (P14, 9 July, 2025, 13.20pm).

Adoption of resource optimization strategies in public service delivery

There should be proper strategies of managing scarce resources such as reducing operational inefficiencies, minimize wastage and maintain continuity of resources. It was revealed in interview that, the appropriate use of resources in administration is very important. The effectiveness and efficient use of resources required to be maintained internally for the achievement of the desirable outcomes. The assignment of resources should be taken a guarantee where are mostly needed. This was included the attainment of proper plan and allocation of resources as well as consistency monitoring and evaluation. It should also involve continuous tracking of employees' performance. However, this finding was essential for aligning with the national regulation policy, public standards and reduces over reliance on unpredictable external funding. One female participant shared that:

“As we know always resources are not enough, it required to be used effectively such that, there should involves strong strategic effort to minimize expenses” (P1, 2 July, 2025, 9:30am).

Advocacy and external support in public service delivery

The need of involving advocacy and external support in public service delivery was recognized during interview. It was provided as advice to the local government officials for the proper improvement of administrative service. This should include the NGOs or donor funding and community-based organization through which support the Council to fill the funding gap in Ilala City Council. The study emphasizes the adoption of advocacy and external support so as to reduce financial burden in the Council and to create more opportunities for sustainable administrative service enhancement. Relevantly, one male interviewee said

“There should be an extra effort in looking for external investors who are willing to provide financial support and we require to use our advocates effectively whoever required to do so” (P7, 8 July, 2025, 14:20pm).

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The study assessed the status of funding for public service delivery. The findings of this study revealed about the causes of inadequate funds for public service delivery on the base of administrative service delivery. The study also indicated the existence of the effects of inadequate funding as well as the measures taken for enhancement of public service delivery. The findings of this study produced in a great involvement of the described methodology for the consistence and accurate results. However, this study contributes excessively in improving administrative service delivery specifically to Ilala City Council. Apart from that, the study contributes in developing new theoretical ideas which are very relevant to the study of governance and public administration.

5.2 Recommendations

Basing on the objectives of the study of assessing the status of funding for public service delivery, this study recommends the following.

The government should practice continuous general auditing. This should involve regular and systematic assessment of financial, operational and performance in public service delivery. This is so important in improving the budget management and for enhancing the community trust.

The government should develop an alternative measure on allocating sufficient budget for the public service delivery. This should involve also the allocation of emergence funds through which will be useful in taking precaution for the emergence of new demands and it should be taken whenever it mostly needed.

There should be a creation of proper system and framework. This was for overcoming the long waiting hours challenge and to ensure well implementation of internal revenue collection policy. This challenge became common in public service delivery in which resulting into dissatisfaction, inefficient and reduces the quality of service. In establishing proper system and framework will play a great role in enhancing service delivery. This could be done by introducing service time standards for different service.

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